

Multiphysics Modelling of an Ultra-High Temperature Storage integrated in the SUNSON-BOX Solar-To-Heat-To-Power system

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Abstract — The design modelled in the present work incorporates concentrated solar power (CSP) into a compact ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage (UHT-LHTES) system. This Solar-to-Heat-to-Power (S2H2P) system utilizes Phase Change Materials (PCM) as core storage and a solid-state generator based on Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells. Operation at ultra-high temperature levels (over 1200°C) enables a significantly more compact compared to traditional CSP storage. This solution aligns with the European strategy's emphasis on the flexibility and dispatchability of renewable energy sources (RES). COMSOL Multiphysics® supports a multiphysics coupling to understand the influence of the key parameters of the system design and materials on the overall performance. The design model is a useful tool to strongly endorse the choice of optimal materials and design configurations. Results revealed the expected thermal cycling periods, temperature mapping, energy and power outputs and system efficiencies. This is the first time that a groundbreaking design of this nature has been simulated using a comprehensive multiphysics model for all the components of a revolutionary S2H2P system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy storage facilitates the integration of renewable energy sources (RES), bolsters system flexibility, and guarantees a reliable energy supply, thereby decreasing reliance on gas power plants [1]. The combination of concentrated solar power (CSP) and thermal energy storage (TES) presents a potentially effective resolution to the issue of intermittent RES availability. TES systems have the potential to offer dispatchability in the absence or reduction of sunlight. In addition, the potential electric energy densities achieved through integrating TES with energy converters, such as thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells, are on par with the highest-quality lithium-ion batteries [2]. Ultra-high temperature latent heat storage (UHT-LHTES) provides enhanced energy densities and improved operational efficiency, implying increased system adaptability and dispatchability [3]. However, its applications remain limited due to significant technological challenges posed by extreme conditions (corrosiveness, scarcity, low availability, thermal expansion, and sustainability implications) that risk its implementation [4].

The innovative design of a Solar-to-Heat-to-Power (S2H2P) system is the SUNSON initiative's foundation [5]. The project proposes the holistic integration of CSP, TPV, and UHT-LHTES with novel phase change materials (PCM) alloys that

operate over 1200°C. Particularly, systems capitalise on the higher melting points of inorganic substances, e.g., silicon, iron, and boron. However, the selection process for PCMs and the design configuration necessitates a detailed assessment of their properties and influence on the overall system performance. The proposed work moves one step beyond the current state-of-the-art simulations by formulating a comprehensive model that considers usually neglected mechanisms such as natural convection and radiative heat transfer [6]. This allows a better comprehension of the complex thermal, material, and electrical system interactions, particularly at high temperatures.

II. SIMULATION MODELLING

The proposed multiphysics model integrates comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and accounts for all heat transfer mechanisms (including surface-to-surface radiation) and natural convection inside the liquid phase of the PCM [7]. COMSOL® 6.2 is used to simulate the system's performance, thereby advancing comprehension and progress of the system. The geometry is simplified using a 3D doubly symmetric simulation. Physics interfaces are configured as laminar flow to describe the fluid motion in the PCM domain (while velocity equals zero in the solid state). The solid-to-liquid transition is defined by a mushy zone resembling a porous material [8]. The Boussinesq approximation addresses natural convection inside the PCM domain as an incompressible fluid, simulating flows driven by buoyancy [9]. The model for the electricity generated by the TPV uses conversion efficiency as a function of the emitter temperature [3]. The method and equations are detailed in reference [10].

The system's structure is embedded within a metal container. The space between the components is filled with multiple thermal insulation layers for high-temperature operation, such as graphite fibre mat or fumed silica board. The system's uppermost part contains the CSP absorbers that provide solar input to the PCM. The crucible (made of silicon carbide and graphite) holds the PCM alloy and transfers heat to and from it. The system's TPV device converts thermal energy into electricity, and the crucible is placed near it for efficient thermal transfer. Insulation in the system's outer wall reduces heat loss.

TABLE I. MAIN SPECIFICATIONS AND PCM PROPERTIES TO SIMULATE THE S2H2P SYSTEM

Key S2H2P system indicator		PCM properties	
Solar input power	47 kW	Volume	0.0124 m ³
Solar irradiance at the aperture	1.2 MW/m ²	Density	2976 kg/m ³
Insulation thermal conductivity	0.05 W/(m·K)	Thermal conductivity @ 20°C	100.67 W/(m·K)
Crucible thermal conductivity	1 W/(m·K)	Latent heat capacity	1669 kJ/kg
TPV cells' power density (dependent on temperature)	~1 W _{el} /cm ²	Sensible heat capacity	1.20 kJ/(kg·K)
TPV cells' surface	100 cm ²	Melting point and range	1340 °C and 60 °C

Table 1 shows the main specifications and PCM properties to simulate the system.

III. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the PCM melt fraction, temperature distribution, and velocity distribution in three different time steps during the charging cycle. The PCM starts to melt from the side near the heat source. After enough material melts, natural convection causes the PCM to melt from higher to lower layers. Whirls, which indicate natural convection, arise when buoyancy fluctuates due to the change in the material's temperature.

Fig. 1. PCM temperature mapping (right legend, °C), melt fraction (left legend, 0-solid 1-liquid) and velocity field (arrows).

Fig. 2 illustrates the PCM's liberated thermal energy and the electrical energy produced by the TPV cell over time in a discharge cycle. The primary cause of the linear rise in the liberated thermal energy is the latent heat of fusion, which is dominant over the sensible heat contribution. Conversely, the occurrence of the accumulated thermal energy plateau can be attributed to the completion of the PCM's solidification.

Fig. 2. Energy performance of the S2H2P-UHTES system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The SUNSON project involves a novel S2H2P system combining UHT-LHTES and CSP as critical technologies to

transition to sustainable energy. The simulation multiphysics model addresses potential design challenges early on, allowing the analysis of behaviour indicators to improve the system performance, focusing on generation efficiencies. The expected results achieved solar-to-thermal conversion efficiencies >45% and thermal-to-electric conversion efficiencies >15%. The simulations showed that the PCM's high operation temperature (1300-1460°C) implies an efficient thermal energy transfer to the TPV generator, increasing electrical output power up to 250 W. Thermal cycle is 0.87 h for charging (with an energy storage capacity of near 20 kWh_{th}) and 3 h for discharging (with an electricity production of around 0.4 kWh_{el}). Thus, the selected PCM (1669 kJ/kg latent storage capacity and melting point at 1340°C) was proven to offer a great performance. Still, further technical and non-technical criteria (non-harmful materials, economic factors) should be considered in system suitability.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission – “REPowerEU Plan - EUR-Lex 52022DC0230”, accessed online: abr. 2024. available link, may. 2022.
- [2] T. Burger et al., “Present Efficiencies and Future Opportunities in TPV,” *Joule*, vol.4-8, aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JOULE.2020.06.021.
- [3] A. Datas et al., “Ultra high temperature latent heat energy storage and thermophotovoltaic energy conversion,” *Energy*, vol. 107, pp. 542–549, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2016.04.048
- [4] P. Royo et al., “High-temperature PCM-based TES for industrial furnaces installed in energy-intensive industries,” *Energy*, vol. 173, pp. 1030–1040, apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2019.02.118.
- [5] SUNSON Project GA ID: 101083827 “Concentrated Solar energy storage at Ultra-high temperatures aNd Solid-state cONversion”, from Horizon Europe Programme, DOI 10.3030/101083827
- [6] M. Zeneli et al., “Numerical simulation of a silicon-based LHTES system operating at UHT,” *Appl Energy*, vol. 242, pp. 837–853, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2019.03.147.
- [7] COMSOL®, “The Heat Transfer Module User’s Guide,” 2022, Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. Available Online: www.comsol.com/blogs
- [8] V. R. Voller et al., “A fixed grid numerical methodology for convection-diffusion mushy region problems,” *Int J Heat Mass Transf*, vol. 30- 8, aug. 1987, doi: 10.1016/0017-9310(87)90317-6.
- [9] COMSOL®, “The CFD Module User’s Guide,” 2022, Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. Available Online: www.comsol.com/blogs.
- [10] A. Hernández et al. ‘Multiphysics Optimisation Model of a UHTES with a Novel S2H2P system. IRES Conf. Proceedings, 2024:

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